

Dithiophosphinates of Some First Row Transition Metals

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The effect of substitution on the phosphorus atom of dithiophosphinates was examined by synthesising complexes of Etdtpi, Cl_2 dtpi and MeCldtpi [where Etdtpi, Cl_2 dtpi and MeCldtpi are di (*p*-ethylphenyl), di (3,4-dichlorophenyl) and di(2-methyl-5-chlorophenyl)dithiophosphinate] with Cr(III), Mn(II), Fe(III), Co(II) and Ni(II). The esr spectra of Fe(III) derivatives were indicative of distortion from octahedral symmetry while for those of Cr(III) derivatives a large reduction of the spin-orbit coupling constant (λ) was observed, indicating the high nephelauxetic effect of these sulphur ligands. Wherever possible the ligand field parameters (10 Dq, B and β) were evaluated and from the 10 Dq values the position of these sulphur ligands were found to be lower in the spectrochemical series compared to many other dithioligands.

THE effect of substituents on the spectral properties of dithiocarbamate complexes has been observed¹. In an earlier communication the stability of cupric dithiophosphinates in relation to the substituents on the phosphorus atom was reported². In view of this it was of interest to investigate the dithio derivatives of some other first row transition metals with various substituted dithiophosphinic acids. The results of such a study on the complexes of Etdtpi, Cl_2 dtpi and MeCldtpi are reported here.

Experimental

The magnetic moment measurements were carried out at room temperature on a Gouy balance using $Hg[Co(SCN)_4]$ as the calibrant. The electronic and esr spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 402 spectrophotometer and E-line Century Series Varian X-band spectrometer respectively.

Preparation of the complexes :

CrX_3 ($X = Etdtpi, Cl_2dtpi$ or $MeCldtpi$) : Methanolic solutions of the sulphur ligands (3.0 g) and chromium chloride hexahydrate (0.7 g) were mixed and refluxed for about 20 min. The bluish violet or violet complexes which separated out were filtered, washed with methanol and recrystallised from chloroform-methanol mixture.

MnX_2 ($X = Etdtpi, Cl_2dtpi$ or $MeCldtpi$) : Methanolic solutions of the sulphur ligands (3.0 g) and $MnCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (0.9 g) were mixed with vigorous stirring. The yellow complexes were washed with methanol and dried under vacuum.

FeX_3 ($X = Etdtpi, Cl_2dtpi$ or $MeCldtpi$) : Excess amount of the methanolic solution of the sodium salt of the sulphur ligands were added to a ferric chloride solution in methanol with vigorous stirring. The black/olive green complexes were filtered, washed with methanol and dried.

$Co(Cl_2dtpi)_2$: The complex was precipitated when an aqueous solution of cobalt chloride hexahydrate (1.4 g) was mixed with $NaCl_2dtpi$ (3.8 g) in water. The dark green complex was filtered and dried. The attempted preparation in methanol resulted in a brown sticky mass of uncertain composition. $Co(Etdtpi)_2$ was prepared in solution by mixing appropriate amount of the methanolic solutions of $CoCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ and EtdtpiH.

$Ni(MeCldtpi)_2$: A methanolic solution of nickel chloride hexahydrate (1.5 g) was added to a methanolic solution of $NaMeCldtpi$ and the precipitated light violet complex was filtered, washed with methanol and dried.

TABLE 1—COLOUR AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	Colour	M	Found (%)				Calcd. (%)			H
			S	C	H	M	S	C		
$Cr(Etdtpi)_2$	Violet	5.52	20.41	57.60	5.32	5.37	19.87	59.57	5.58	
$Cr(Cl_2dtpi)_2$	Bluish violet	4.18	15.61	45.95	1.59	4.29	15.83	35.61	1.48	
$Cr(MeCldtpi)_2$	Violet	4.68	17.49	46.45	3.10	4.77	17.61	46.24	3.30	
$Mn(Etdtpi)_2$	Yellow	8.13	19.38	57.92	5.12	8.27	19.25	57.74	5.41	
$Mn(Cl_2dtpi)_2$	Yellow	6.28	15.64	34.50	1.21	6.65	15.48	34.82	1.45	
$Mn(MeCldtpi)_2$	Brown	7.58	17.62	45.21	3.62	7.36	17.14	44.98	3.21	
$Fe(Etdtpi)_2$	Black	5.83	19.53	59.81	5.35	5.76	19.78	59.33	5.56	
$Fe(Cl_2dtpi)_2$	Olive green	4.69	15.65	35.86	1.27	4.60	15.82	35.59	1.48	
$Fe(MeCldtpi)_2$	Olive green	5.32	17.86	46.18	3.08	5.11	17.55	46.07	3.29	
$Co(Cl_2dtpi)_2$	Dark green	6.92	15.49	45.20	2.94	7.08	15.37	44.80	3.20	
$Ni(MeCldtpi)_2$	Light violet	7.82	17.18	33.80	1.52	7.68	17.05	34.60	1.44	

TABLE 2—MAGNETIC MOMENTS AND THE SOLUTION SPECTRAL DATA* OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	Magnetic moment (B.M.)	Band maxima (cm ⁻¹)
Cr(Etdtpi) ₃	3.83	13620, 17860, 18950(sh)
Cr(Cl ₂ dtpi) ₃	3.90	13890, 18180, 19230(sh)
Cr(MeClDtpi) ₃	3.86	13900, 18180, 19220(sh)
Mn(Etdtpi) ₃	5.81	21100
Mn(Cl ₂ dtpi) ₂	5.85	17540(sh), 21200
Mn(MeClDtpi) ₂	5.80	21700
Fe(Etdtpi) ₃	—	16600, 19000, 23500
Fe(Cl ₂ dtpi) ₃	5.57	16260, 19050, 23800
Fe(MeClDtpi) ₃	5.80	14900(sh), 17540(sh), 22730
Co(Etdtpi) ₂	—	14900
Co(Cl ₂ dtpi) ₂	4.45	15000
Ni(Etdtpi) ₂	—	13700, 17900
Ni(MeClDtpi) ₂	—	13890, 18180

*All the spectra were recorded in chloroform.

The analytical data of the complexes are given in Table 1 and magnetic moment and solution spectra in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

Cr(III) complexes : The complexes were soluble in organic solvents and had room temperature magnetic moments in the range 3.83-3.90 B.M. obtained by the Gouy's method. This was in good agreement with those obtained by Evans' nmr technique⁸ (3.77-3.81 B.M.). The electronic spectra were typical of octahedral CrS₆ core complex showing intense absorptions around 13620-13900 cm⁻¹ and 17860-18180 cm⁻¹ corresponding to ⁴A_{2g}→⁴T_{2g} and ⁴A_{2g}→⁴T_{1g} (F) transitions respectively. The shoulders observed around 18950-19230 cm⁻¹ may originate due to a trigonal split component of the ⁴A_{2g}→⁴T_{1g}(F) transition or can be due to a spin forbidden quartet-doublet transition⁴.

The high value of the oscillator strength (Table 3) reflect the pronounced covalency in the metal-ligand bond. The 10 Dq values (13620-13900 cm⁻¹) were evaluated from the first spin allowed transition and using equation for B, the values of Racah parameter (399-402 cm⁻¹) were obtained. A comparison of the 10 Dq and B values (Table 3) suggest that the substitution in the benzene nucleus attached to the phosphorus atom does not significantly influence the ligand field parameters.

TABLE 3—LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS OF Cr(III) and Co(II) COMPLEXES*

Complex	10 Dq(cm ⁻¹)	B(cm ⁻¹)	β	Oscillator strength	λ (cm ⁻¹)
Cr(Etdtpi) ₃	13620	399	0.43	365 (13620), 367 (17860)	28
Cr(Cl ₂ dtpi) ₃	13890	402	0.43	379 (13890), 370 (18180)	38
Cr(MeClDtpi) ₃	13900	401	0.43	419 (13900), 365 (18180)	38
Co(Etdtpi) ₂	3950	763	0.67	—	—
Co(Cl ₂ dtpi) ₂	3702	793	0.70	—	-124

* Oscillator strengths were calculated from the relation $f = 4.6 \times 10^{-9} \epsilon_{max} \nu_{1/2}$, ϵ_{max} = molar extinction coefficient $\nu_{1/2}$ = band width at the half height in wave numbers. The bands oscillator strengths are given in parenthesis.

with a peak to peak separation of 300 G were obtained. The *g*_{isotropic} values were calculated to be 1.98±0.01. The large reduction of the spin-orbit coupling constant (28-38 cm⁻¹) compared to the free ion value (90 cm⁻¹) is a measure of metal-ligand covalency and was in good agreement with the high nephelauxetic effect of these sulphur ligands.

Mn(II) complexes : Among the manganese(II) dithio derivatives Mn(Etdtpi)₃ was found to be unstable. Mn(Cl₂dtpi)₂ and Mn(MeClDtpi)₂ had low solubility in non-polar solvents with room temperature magnetic moments in the range of 5.80-5.85 B.M. and the electronic spectra in chloroform showed a band around 21000 cm⁻¹ which could be due to a d-d transition. The esr spectra of the powder samples showed only a single line. However, when diluted with analogous zinc matrix, six hyperfine lines (I=5/2) were observed with g and A values in the ranges 2.02-2.03 and 80-95 (Gauss) respectively.

Fe(III) complexes : The black Fe(Etdtpi)₃ was found to be unstable whereas Fe(Cl₂dtpi)₃ and Fe(MeClDtpi)₃ were stable but decomposed on prolonged exposure to air, similar to other ferric dithio complexes. The room temperature magnetic moments were in the range of 5.57-5.80 B.M. and bands around 16000, 19000 and 23500 cm⁻¹ were observed in the electronic spectra. The esr spectra of the powder samples both at room temperature as well as at 77°K showed three g-values (in the range of 7.38-7.67, 4.26-4.27 and 1.92-1.98) which reflect distortion from octahedral symmetry⁵.

Co(II) complexes : Although dithiophosphinates, unlike other dithioligands, have been observed to form stable complexes of cobalt(II), it is of interest to note that in the present work only Co(Cl₂dtpi)₂ could be isolated in the solid state and Co(Etdtpi)₂ was studied in solution, the analogous derivative with MeClDtpi could not be formed

The magnetic moment of Co(Cl₂dtpi)₂ at room temperature was found to be 4.45 B.M., indicative of a tetrahedral geometry and the electronic spectrum in chloroform was typical of CoS₄ chromophore showing a multicomponent band

The esr spectra of the powder samples were recorded at room temperature and broad signals centered around 15000 cm⁻¹ which was assigned to ⁴A₂→⁴T₁(P) transition⁶. Using equations given

elsewhere⁷ the 10 Dq and B values were calculated to be 3702 and 793 cm⁻¹ respectively. Similar results were obtained for Co(Etdtpi)₂ as given in Table 3. The value of the nephelauxetic parameter β was evaluated to be 0.70 and 0.67 for Co(Cl₂dtpi)₂ and Co(Etdtpi)₂ respectively. Using⁷ the magnetic data and Dq values λ was obtained as -124 cm⁻¹ for Co(Cl₂dtpi)₂ and the reduction in its magnitude from the free-ion value (-178 cm⁻¹) indicated a substantial metal-ligand covalency.

Ni(II) complexes: Ni(MeCl₂dtpi)₂ was isolated in the solid state while Ni(Etdtpi)₂ could be studied in solution and with Cl₂dtpi no complex was formed. The solution spectra of Ni(MeCl₂dtpi)₂ and Ni(Etdtpi)₂ in chloroform showed bands around 13890, 18180 cm⁻¹ and 13700 and 17900 cm⁻¹ respectively which are diagnostic⁸ of a diamagnetic square planar structure. The lowest transitions at 13700 and 13890 cm⁻¹ were assigned to d_{x²-y²} → d_{xy} transition in a D_{2h} symmetry. The 10 Dq values (16500 and 16690 cm⁻¹) were calculated by using

relations given elsewhere⁹ and are in agreement with the position of dithiophosphinates in the spectrochemical series¹⁰.

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